

Palladium(II) complexes of pyrazolate ligands with thioether chelate arms[†]

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Abstract : Two 3,5-disubstituted pyrazole derivatives with one (HL¹) or two (HL²) thioether functions per side arm have been used as ligands towards Ag^I and Pd^{II} ions. Both form the metallamacrocyclic complexes [AgL^{1/2}]₃ (1, 3) with a common [Ag(μ-pz)₃] core. In the presence of excess Ag^I in acetone solution, 3 converts into hexametallallic [Ag₆(L²)₂(acetone)₆](BF₄)₄ (4). Upon treatment with [Pd(MeCN)₄](BF₄)₂, both 1 and 3 readily undergo transmetalation to dinuclear complexes with the general formula [Pd₂L₂](BF₄)₂ (2, 5) having a favorable bis(pyrazolato)-bridged {Pd₂N₄S₄} core structure and dangling thioether arms. Complexes 2, 4, and 5 have been structurally authenticated by X-ray diffraction. ESI mass spectrometry and NMR spectroscopy have revealed that the complexes largely retain their integrity in MeCN solutions.

Keywords : Palladium(II), pyrazolate, thioether, chelate, complexes.

Introduction

Pyrazolates are among the most popular ligands in coordination chemistry¹. In the presence of main group or *d*-block metal ions, they can adopt up to 20 different coordination modes using one or both of the N atoms, or a combination of the N and C atoms, or the π system^{1b}. Their coordination ability has been further elaborated by introducing substituents with additional donor sites in the 3- and 5-positions of the heterocycle². These multidentate compartmental ligands have been exploited for the preparation of highly preorganized pyrazolate-bridged bimetallic complexes that feature tunable cooperativity of the proximate metal ions. Such systems have been beneficially used for, *inter alia*, emulating functional aspects of binuclear metalloprotein active sites³, achieving the synergistic activation and transformation of substrates⁴, and constructing spin-coupled systems for applications in the field of molecule-based magnetism⁵. Some years ago we introduced the use of pyrazoles with thioether chelate arms in the coordination chemistry of monovalent coinage metal ions⁶. In this way, the classical trimeric or tetrameric metallacycles [M(μ-pz)]_n (n = 3, 4; M = Cu^I, Ag^I, Au^I), usually formed by pyrazolate ligands⁷, could

be decorated with a second ring of coinage metal ions by involving the thioether donors, and either octa-⁸ or hexametallallic⁹ complexes were isolated. These compounds showed multiple intra- and intermolecular d¹⁰-d¹⁰ contacts, and their interesting luminescence properties have been emphasized. Recent work of Fujita and coworkers¹⁰ described the synthesis of supramolecular Au₃ stacks capped by tray-shaped Pd^{II}₃Au^I₃ complexes that contain a [Au(μ-pz)]₃ core based on 3,5-bis(3-pyridyl)pyrazolate, with Pd^{II} ions bound to the peripheral pyridyl substituents and serving as clips. Inspired by that report, we decided to test the possibility of isolating heterometallic complexes containing coinage metal [M(μ-pz)]_n units and Pd^{II} ions as linkers, by using pyrazolate/thioether hybrid ligands. In this contribution we describe the results obtained with proligands HL¹ and HL² (Fig. 1) that differ by the number of thioether donor sites per chelate arm. HL² is a new ligand that provides two potentially tridentate {NS₂} binding sites for metal ions. Both HL¹ and HL² are equipped with peripheral 4-fluorophenyl substituents to enable the use of ¹⁹F NMR spectroscopy as an analytical probe for studying the resulting complexes in solution.

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

Fig. 1. The two pyrazole proligands HL¹ and HL² with appended thioether side-arms used in this work.

Results and discussion

The synthesis of proligand HL¹ was previously reported⁸. In its anionic form, [L¹]⁻, it spans two Ag^I ions to form the common planar trimeric complex [AgL¹]₃ (**1**; Fig. 2⁸).

Fig. 2. Sketch of the molecular structure of [AgL¹]₃⁸.

In [AgL¹]₃ the sulfur atoms are not involved in metal ion coordination and are still available as potential donor sites. It was reasoned that the coordination sphere of a Pd^{II} ion could be filled by four thioether-S atoms originating from two different trimers [AgL¹]₃, potentially giving a supramolecular array of two [Ag(μ-pz)]₃ decks linked by Pd^{II} ions as clips. Reaction between **1** and [Pd(MeCN)₄](BF₄)₂ in a 1 : 1.5 molar ratio in a CH₂Cl₂/MeCN mixture yielded a yellow solution. Layering the reaction mixture with Et₂O gave, after few days, single crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction. In contrast to expectations, X-ray crystallography revealed the formation of a complex [Pd₂L¹]₂(BF₄)₂ (**2**) which not only was devoid of the original [AgL¹]₃ core but did not contain any Ag^I ions at all. The molecular structure of the cation of **2** is depicted in Fig. 3.

In [Pd₂L¹]₂²⁺ two Pd^{II} ions are each coordinated by two pyrazolato-N and two thioether-S atoms from two different [L¹]⁻ ligand strands in an almost square planar coordination geometry (bond angles at the Pd^{II} ions in

Fig. 3. Plot (30% probability thermal ellipsoids) of the molecular structure of the cationic part of **2** (hydrogen atoms and disorder omitted for clarity).

the range 84–99°). The central {Pd₂N₄S₄} core of the complex is roughly planar, and the 4-fluorophenyl substituents at the four thioether-S atoms are all oriented towards the same face of this plane. The intramolecular Pd···Pd separation is 3.96 Å. In the solid state this complex differs from the classical structures adopted by Pd^{II} pyrazolato complexes, which are known to exist either as polymeric chains or trimetallic macrocycles^{1b,11}. The ESI mass spectrum of a MeCN solution of **2** (Fig. S6) showed dominant peaks for the expected species [Pd₂L¹]₂²⁺ (*m/z* = 435.9) and [Pd₂L¹]₂(BF₄)⁺ (*m/z* = 994.9), suggesting the integrity of the [Pd₂L¹]₂²⁺ core in solution. However, few more minor signals of Pd-containing species, in particular a peak envelope at high *m/z* values (1710.9), were also present (Fig. S6). Based on the crystallographic structure, high symmetry on the NMR time scale and a rather simple ¹H NMR spectrum were anticipated for the [Pd₂L¹]₂²⁺ cation. Instead, a plethora of signals was observed for a CD₃CN solution of **2** (Fig. S1), indicating a more complex situation. We attribute this to slow dynamic processes within the ligand side arms that lead to isomers with different dispositions of the 4-fluorophenyl substituents with respect to the central {Pd₂N₄S₄} plane, related by inversion of the pyramidal configuration at the coordinated thioether-S¹². Accordingly, at least five distinct resonances for the 4-fluorophenyl group are discernible within a very narrow chemical shift range in the ¹⁹F NMR spectrum of a CD₃CN solution of crystalline **2** (Fig. S2). Taken together the NMR spectroscopy and ESI mass spectrometry results suggest high stability of the [Pd₂L¹]₂²⁺ complex core in MeCN solutions, but with equilibration to several diastereomers.

However, further equilibria giving additional minor species with different connectivity and nuclearity cannot be ruled out either.

Since the $[L^1]^-$ ligand showed a preference of binding Pd^{II} ions at the expense of Ag^I , leading to disassembly of the $[Ag(\mu\text{-pz})_3]$ metallamacrocycle, a new pyrazole-based proligand HL^2 with multidentate thioether side arms was developed. It was reasoned that the presence of additional donor sites might allow obtaining multimetallic compounds that contain both Ag^I and Pd^{II} ions. The new side arm precursor **II** was obtained in a two steps synthesis by modifying some literature known procedures¹³. 2-Chloroethanol and 4-fluorothiophenol in the presence of KOH yielded the alcohol intermediate **I** which was then chlorinated with $SOCl_2$ and finally thiolated by using thio-urea and NaOH, affording **II** (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Synthesis of the side arms precursor **II**.

II was reacted with the pyrazole building block **III**¹⁴ yielding, after acidic deprotection, the target proligand HL^2 (Scheme 2).

HL^2 was initially tested as ligand towards Ag^I ions. Its reaction with Ag_2O in refluxing CH_2Cl_2 gave a new complex (**3**), which is proposed to have the trimeric $[AgL^2]_3$ structure in analogy to compound **1** (Fig. 2) with the thioether side arms dangling. The thioether-S donor sites could indeed be involved in binding additional Ag^I ions by reacting $[AgL^2]_3$ with six equivalents of $AgBF_4$. A 1H NMR spectrum of the white solid product (**4**), recorded in acetone- d_6 or CD_3OD at 298 K, showed a broad peak associated with the two protons of the methylene linker of the side arms, next to the pyrazole heterocycle (Fig. S3, top), indicating the presence of a dynamic process. Decoalescence into two distinct doublets was observed when recording the spectrum at 273 K (Fig. S3, bottom).

Scheme 2. Synthesis of the proligand HL^2 .

These two doublets with an AB-type pattern indicate the formation of a less symmetric complex than the metallamacrocyclic precursor **3**, namely a compound that is no longer planar. Unfortunately, mass spectrometry did not provide any further clue about the nuclearity of **4**, because the ESI mass spectrum mainly contained the same peaks already encountered for the precursor **3**. This result was not unexpected for such pyrazolate/thioether hybrid ligands as previous investigations had shown that any additional S-bound Ag^I ions are labile in coordinating solvents such as MeCN or MeOH usually employed in ESI-MS experiments⁸. Single crystals of **4** were grown from acetone/hexane at 5 °C, and X-ray diffraction revealed the formation of a compound with the formula $[Ag_6(L^2)_2(acetone)_6](BF_4)_4$ (Fig. 4). Its central core contains four Ag^I , each two of them spanned by a N,N'-bridging pyrazolate and coordinated by a thioether-S from the other $[L^2]^-$ ligand. Their coordination sphere is completed by a weakly bound O-bridging acetone molecule, resulting in a distorted trigonal $\{2+1\}$ geometry around the metal ions. The four central Ag^I ions are located in a plane with $Ag\cdots Ag$ distances of 3.57 Å and 3.03 Å (Fig. 4). Two additional Ag^I ions are linearly bound by the remaining outer thioether-S atoms of the side arms; their ligation sphere is again complemented by weakly bound acetone molecules, giving an overall $\{2+2\}$ coordination environment. Because of the high number of acetone molecules that is directly coordinated to the six Ag^I ions in **4**,

Fig. 4. Plot (30% probability thermal ellipsoids) of the molecular structure of the cationic part of **4** (hydrogen atoms omitted for clarity).

the structure of the complex that forms from $[L^2]^-$ and an excess of Ag^I ions is likely dependent on the solvent employed during the crystallization process. The use of less coordinating solvents or of different crystallization techniques (e.g. sublimation) might thus lead to the isolation of a different molecular structure of the compound, but our limited attempts in that direction were so far unsuccessful.

In order to test whether the higher number of thioether-S donors in HL^2 , compared to HL^1 , might prevent the complete replacement of Ag^I ions upon treatment with Pd^{II} , **4** was reacted with three equivalents of $[Pd(MeCN)_4](BF_4)_2$, affording $[Pd_2L^1_2](BF_4)_2$ (**5**). It was of particular interest to see whether Pd^{II} would occupy sites with N/S or S/S chelate ligation, as both possibilities give rise to 5-membered chelate rings. Single crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction were obtained by layering Et_2O above a solution of crude **5** in MeCN. The molecular structure of **5** revealed the formation of a dimeric complex $[Pd_2L^1_2]^{2+}$ with a structure akin to the structure of **2**. Two Pd^{II} ions are found in a $\{N_2S_2\}$ environment, formed by two $[L^2]^-$ ligand strands, in a (only slightly distorted) square planar geometry (Fig. 5). The additional

sulfur atoms of the ligand side arms are not involved in any additional metal ion binding, and the product does not contain any Ag^I ions. As discussed above, the absence of Ag^I ions in the molecular structure of **5** is most likely due to the solvents employed during the crystallization process. In fact, in a coordinating solvent such as MeCN the purely S-bound Ag^I ions can be easily removed⁸. The use of less coordinating solvents might well lead to the formation of heterometallic complexes containing both Pd^{II} and Ag^I ions, but all efforts directed at isolating such species were so far unsuccessful. The ESI mass spectrum of a solution of **5** in MeCN (Fig. S7) showed dominant signals for the species $[Pd_2L^2_2]^{2+}$ ($m/z = 650.0$) and $[Pd_2L^2_2(BF_4)]^+$ ($m/z = 1387.0$), suggesting that the $[Pd_2L^2_2]^{2+}$ core remains intact under those conditions, similar to what was observed for **2**. Again, the 1H NMR spectra of crystalline **5** in CD_3CN and acetone- d_6 solutions were more complicated than expected (Figs. S4 and S5). In particular, the multiple signals associated with the protons of the side arm methylene linkers next to the pyrazolate heterocycle were clearly in disagreement with the presence of a (time-averaged) planar $[Pd_2L^2_2]^{2+}$ structure. We assume that several isomers with different dis-

Fig. 5. Plot (30% probability thermal ellipsoids) of the molecular structure of the cationic part of **5** (hydrogen atoms and disorder omitted for clarity).

positions of the dangling outer side arms with respect to the central $\{Pd_2N_4S_4\}$ core are present, and that their interconversion via inversion at the inner coordinating thioether-S atoms is slow on the NMR time scale¹².

Conclusion

We have here reported the use of pyrazolate-based ligands with appended thioether side arms in the coordination chemistry of Pd^{II} ions, including the new proligand HL² that has two thioether functions per arm. The chelating N/S sites provided by both ligands [L¹]⁻ and [L²]⁻ seem highly suited to bind Pd^{II} ions in square-planar environment, giving in both cases a stable bis(pyrazolato)-bridged $\{Pd_2N_4S_4\}$ arrangement with *trans*-disposed pyrazolato-N and thioether-S donors at the Pd^{II} centers. Coordination of Pd^{II} obviously is highly favored over Ag^I binding, causing disassembly of the metallomacrocyclic $[Ag(\mu\text{-pz})_3]$ cores of the $[AgL^{1/2}]_3$ precursor complexes upon addition of $[Pd(MeCN)_4](BF_4)_2$. In coordinating MeCN solvent this leads to complete expulsion of all Ag^I ions via transmetalation to give $[Pd_2L^1_2]^{2+}$ and $[Pd_2L^2_2]^{2+}$. NMR spectroscopy and ESI mass spectrometry have provided evidence the $[Pd_2L^1_2]^{2+}$ and $[Pd_2L^2_2]^{2+}$ complexes largely retain their integrity in MeCN or acetone solutions, though several isomers seem

to be present. On the other hand, the structure of the homometallic hexasilver complex $[Ag_6(L^2)_2(\text{acetone})_6](BF_4)_4$ has illustrated that the thioether-S of the ligand side arms are, in principle, capable of hosting Ag^I ions in a roughly linear S-Ag-S arrangement, which might offer some perspective for synthesizing heterobimetallic Pd^{II}/Ag^I cluster complexes after proper optimization of reaction conditions.

Experimental

Methods and materials :

Hexane was dried over sodium in the presence of benzophenone, MeCN and CH₂Cl₂ were dried over CaH₂; all solvents were distilled prior to use.

NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker Avance 300 MHz, Bruker Avance 400 MHz and Bruker DRX 500 MHz spectrometers at 298 K. Chemical shifts (δ) are reported in ppm relative to residual proton and carbon signal of the solvent (CDCl₃: δ_H = 7.26, δ_C = 77.16 ppm; acetone-*d*₆: δ_H = 2.05, δ_C = 29.84 ppm; CD₃CN: δ_H = 1.94, δ_C = 1.32 ppm; methanol-*d*₄: δ_H = 3.31, δ_C = 49.00 ppm).

EI mass spectra were recorded with a Finnigan MAT 8200. ESI mass spectra were recorded with an Applied Biosystems API 2000 and a BRUKER HCT ultra.

The pyrazole building block **III** was obtained following literature known procedures¹⁴. Ligand HL¹ and complex [AgL¹]₃ (**I**) were synthesized as previously reported⁸.

Precursor and ligands :

2-(4-Fluorophenylthio)ethanol (I) : 4-Fluorothiophenol (7.5 g, 58.5 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and KOH (3.3 g, 58.8 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) were dissolved in EtOH (60 mL) under an argon atmosphere. The solution was stirred for 1 h at 50 °C and 2-chloroethanol (4.8 g, 59.6 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) was added. The resulting mixture was heated to reflux for 5 h, cooled to room temperature and filtered. The solvent of the filtrate was removed under reduced pressure and the resulting oil was dried *in vacuo* and used for the next step without any further purification (9.6 g, 55.7 mmol, 95%). ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 2.74 (1H, b, OH), 3.01 (2H, t, ³J_{H-H} 6.1 Hz, SCH₂), 3.67 (2H, t, ³J_{H-H} 6.1 Hz, CH₂OH), 6.97 (2H, dd, ³J_{H-H} 9 Hz, ³J_{H-F} 8.4 Hz, 3-H^{Ar}), 7.36 (2H, dd, ³J_{H-H} 9 Hz, ⁴J_{H-F} 5.2 Hz, 2-H^{Ar}); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 38.2 (SCH₂), 60.3 (CH₂OH), 116.2 (d, ²J_{C-F} 21.75 Hz, 3-C^{Ar}), 129.9 (d, ⁴J_{C-F} 3.4 Hz, 1-C^{Ar}), 133.1 (d, ³J_{C-F} 8 Hz, 2-C^{Ar}), 162.1 (d, ¹J_{C-F} 246 Hz, 4-C^{Ar}); ¹⁹F NMR (282 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : -114.7 (Ar-F); MS (EI) : *m/z* (%) = 45.0 (30), 128.0 [HSC₆H₄F]⁺ (35), 141.0 [M-CH₂OH]⁺ (100), 172.0 [M]⁺ (94).

2-(4-Fluorophenylthio)ethanethiol (II) : SOCl₂ (20 mL) was added to **I** (9.0 g, 52.3 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) and the solution was heated to reflux for 5 h. Excess thionyl chloride was removed by distillation, the residue was dissolved in EtOH (20 mL) and thiourea (4.4 g, 57.8 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) was added. The mixture was heated to reflux under an argon atmosphere for 36 h, cooled to room temperature and a solution of NaOH (4.2 g, 105 mmol, 2.0 equiv.) in degassed water was added. The resulting solution was heated at 80 °C for 3 h, cooled to 0 °C and acidified with HCl 37% causing the formation of two phases. The lower layer was separated and distilled in a Kugelrohr apparatus (100 °C, 1 × 10⁻² mbar) to give **II** as colorless oil (5.12 g, 27.2 mmol, 52%). The aqueous layer was extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 × 30 mL), the organic part was dried with Na₂SO₄, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was distilled via Kugelrohr (100 °C, 1 × 10⁻² mbar) allowing to obtain additional 675 mg of **II**. The overall yield is 5.795

g (30.8 mmol, 57%). ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 1.70 (1H, t, ³J_{H-H} 8.2 Hz, SH), 2.64–2.72 (2H, m, CH₂SH), 3.03–3.09 (2H, m, SCH₂), 7.01 (2H, t, ³J_{H-H} = ³J_{H-F} 8.7 Hz, 3-H^{Ar}), 7.33 (2H, dd, ³J_{H-H} 8.7 Hz, ⁴J_{H-F} 5.2 Hz, 2-H^{Ar}); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 24.3 (CH₂SH), 39.48 (CH₂S^{Ar}), 116.4 (d, ²J_{C-F} 21.9 Hz, 3-C^{Ar}), 129.8 (d, ⁴J_{C-F} 3.4 Hz, 1-C^{Ar}), 133.6 (d, ³J_{C-F} 8.1 Hz, 2-C^{Ar}), 162.3 (d, ¹J_{C-F} 246 Hz, 4-C^{Ar}); ¹⁹F NMR (282 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : -114.5 (Ar-F); MS (EI) : *m/z* (%) = 61.0 [CH₂CH₂SH]⁺ (30), 128.0 [HSC₆H₄F]⁺ (100), 141.0 [M-CH₂SH]⁺ (24), 188.0 [M]⁺ (40).

HL² : A solution of **II** (1.62 g, 8.6 mmol, 2.0 equiv.) in THF (20 mL) was deprotonated at -20 °C with a stoichiometric amount of *n*-BuLi (1.6 M in hexane) and stirred for 1 h. A solution of **III** (1.40 g, 4.3 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) in THF (20 mL) was added and the resulting solution was stirred at room temperature overnight. All volatile materials were then removed *in vacuo* and the residue dissolved in EtOH (40 mL) and ethanolic HCl (20 mL). After stirring for 2 h at room temperature, NaOH (4 M) was added until pH > 9 and the resulting solution was extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 × 100 mL). Organic phases were collected, dried over Na₂SO₄ and the solvent was evaporated. The crude material was purified via column chromatography using hexane/AcOEt 3 : 2 as eluent (*R_f* = 0.34) to give a yellow oil that solidified upon standing (1.62 g, 2.97 mmol, 69%). ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 2.61–2.66 (4H, m, CH₂CH₂S^{Ar}), 2.86–2.91 (4H, m, CH₂CH₂S^{Ar}), 3.73 (4H, s, CH₂^{Pz}), 6.97 (4H, t, ³J_{H-H} = ³J_{H-F} 8.7 Hz, 3-H^{Ar}), 7.28–7.44 (9H, m, 2-H^{Ar}, H^{Ph}); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 26.2 (CH₂^{Pz}), 31.5 (CH₂CH₂S^{Ar}), 35.1 (CH₂CH₂S^{Ar}), 116.3 (d, ²J_{C-F} 21.9 Hz, 3-C^{Ar}), 127.5 (4-C^{Ph}), 129.0 (2-C^{Ph}), 129.9 (3-C^{Ph}), 130.2 (d, ⁴J_{C-F} 3.2 Hz, 1-C^{Ar}), 132.0 (1-C^{Ph}), 133.2 (d, ³J_{C-F} 8 Hz, 2-C^{Ar}); the remaining quaternary carbon atoms could not be detected. ¹⁹F NMR (282 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : -115.0 (Ar-F); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 2.64–2.70 (4H, m, CH₂CH₂S^{Ar}), 2.98 (4H, t, ³J_{H-H} 7.8 Hz, CH₂CH₂S^{Ar}), 3.80 (4H, s, CH₂^{Pz}), 7.10 (4H, t, ³J_{H-H} = ³J_{H-F} 8.9 Hz, 3-H^{Ar}), 7.30–7.49 (9H, m, 2-H^{Ar}, H^{Ph}), 12.02 (1H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 31.9 (CH₂CH₂S^{Ar}), 35.0 (CH₂CH₂S^{Ar}), 116.8 (d, ²J_{C-F} 21.8 Hz, 3-C^{Ar}), 119.7 (4-C^{Pz}), 127.6 (4-C^{Ph}), 129.5 (2-C^{Ph}),

130.6 (3-C^{Ph}, 1-C^{Ar}), 131.9 (1-C^{Ph}), 133.2 (d, $^3J_{C-F}$ 7.5 Hz, 2-C^{Ar}), 134.0, 162.6 (d, $^1J_{C-F}$ 243 Hz, 4-C^{Ar}); the signal of the CH₂^{Pz} groups was overlapped by the solvent peak; the 3/5-C^{Pz} carbon atoms could not be detected. ¹⁹F NMR (282 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : -117.4 (Ar-F); MS (ESI+, MeOH) : *m/z* (%) = 545.1 [M+H]⁺ (100), 567.1 [M+Na]⁺ (16), 583.1 [M+K]⁺ (60), 1089.2 [2M+H]⁺ (28), 1111.2 [2M+Na]⁺ (12), 1127.2 [2M+K]⁺ (20). EA Calcd. (%) for C₂₇H₂₆F₂N₂S₄: C, 59.53; H, 4.81; N, 5.14; S, 23.54. Found : C, 59.21; H, 4.79; N, 4.96; S, 23.46.

Complexes :

[Pd₂(L¹)₂](BF₄)₂ (2) : A solution of [Pd(MeCN)₄](BF₄)₂ (13 mg, 29.3 × 10⁻³ mmol, 1.5 equiv.) in CH₂Cl₂ (4 mL) and MeCN (1 mL) was added to a solution of [AgL¹]₃ (27 mg, 19.8 × 10⁻³ mmol, 1.0 equiv.) in CH₂Cl₂ (5 mL). The resulting mixture was stirred for 2 h. Yellow crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction were obtained by layering Et₂O over the reaction mixture. ¹⁹F NMR (470 MHz, CD₃CN) δ (ppm) : -151.76 (¹¹BF₄), -151.70 (¹⁰BF₄), -108.16, -108.01, -107.81, -107.45 (Ar-F); MS (ESI+, MeCN) : *m/z* (%) = 453.9 [Pd₂L₂]²⁺ (100), 805.0 (10), 908.9 (5), 994.9 [Pd₂L₂(BF₄)]⁺ (8), 1710.9 (7).

[AgL²]₃ (3) : Silver(I) oxide (35 mg, 0.151 mmol, 0.6 equiv.) was added to a solution of HL² (137 mg, 0.251 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) in CH₂Cl₂ (30 mL) and the mixture was heated to reflux for one day under exclusion of light. The reaction mixture was then treated with activated carbon and filtered over Celite 545. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the resulting yellowish semisolid oil was dried *in vacuo* (150 mg, 0.0767 mmol, 92%). ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 2.57–2.62 (4H, m, CH₂CH₂S^{Ar}), 2.74–2.79 (4H, m, CH₂CH₂S^{Ar}), 3.84 (4H, s, CH₂^{Pz}), 6.91 (4H, t, $^3J_{H-H} = ^3J_{H-F}$ 8.7 Hz, 3-H^{Ar}), 7.19–7.24 (6H, m, 2-H^{Ar}, 3-H^{Ph}), 7.32 (1H, t, $^3J_{H-H}$ 7.2 Hz, 4-H^{Ph}), 7.41 (2H, t, $^3J_{H-H}$ 7.2 Hz, 2-H^{Ph}); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 28.0 (CH₂^{Pz}), 31.4 (CH₂CH₂S^{Ar}), 34.9 (CH₂CH₂S^{Ar}), 116.3 (d, $^2J_{C-F}$ 21.8 Hz, 3-C^{Ar}), 119.5 (4-C^{Pz}), 126.8 (4-C^{Ph}), 128.9 (2-C^{Ph}), 130.0 (3-C^{Ph}), 130.2 (d, $^4J_{C-F}$ 4 Hz, 1-C^{Ar}), 133.0 (d, $^3J_{C-F}$ 7.5 Hz, 2-C^{Ar}), 133.8 (1-C^{Ph}), 146.4 (3/5-C^{Pz}), 162.1 (d, $^1J_{C-F}$ 246 Hz, 4-C^{Ar}); ¹⁹F NMR (282 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : -114.8 (Ar-F); ¹H NMR

(300 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 2.68–2.72 (4H, m, CH₂CH₂S^{Ar}), 2.87–2.92 (4H, m, CH₂CH₂S^{Ar}), 3.91 (4H, s, CH₂^{Pz}), 7.01 (4H, t, $^3J_{H-H} = ^3J_{H-F}$ 8.9 Hz, 3-H^{Ar}), 7.31 (dd, $^3J_{H-H}$ 8.9 Hz, $^4J_{H-F}$ 5.1 Hz, 2-H^{Ar}), 7.34–7.46 (5H, m, H^{Ph}); ¹⁹F NMR (282 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : -116.7 (Ar-F); MS (ESI+, CH₂Cl₂/MeOH) : *m/z* (%) = 567.2 [HL+Na]⁺ (8), 653.0 [AgL+H]⁺ (18), 713.1 [AgL(OAc)+2H]⁺ (7), 1197.2 [AgL₂+2H]⁺ (100), 1303.0 [Ag₂L₂+H]⁺ (36), 1410.9 [Ag₃L₂]⁺ (10). EA Calcd. (%) for C₈₁H₇₅F₆N₆S₁₂Ag₃ : C, 49.77; H, 3.87; N, 4.30; S, 19.68. Found : C, 49.57; H, 4.04; N, 4.15; S, 19.25.

[Ag₆(L²)₂(acetone)₆](BF₄)₄ (4) : A solution of AgBF₄ (23 mg, 0.118 mmol, 3.0 equiv.) in CH₂Cl₂ (3 mL) with few drops of acetone was added to a solution of [AgL²]₃ (2) (75 mg, 38.4 × 10⁻³ mmol, 1.0 equiv.) in CH₂Cl₂ (5 mL). The white suspension which immediately formed was stirred for 2 h under exclusion of light, then the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the resulting white solid dried *in vacuo* (94 mg, 78%). Colorless crystals of the complex [Ag₆L₂₂(acetone)₆](BF₄)₄ suitable for X-ray diffraction were obtained by layering hexane over a solution of the compound in acetone at 5 °C. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 3.24 (4H, b, CH₂CH₂S^{Ar}), 3.40 (4H, b, CH₂CH₂S^{Ar}), 4.41 (4H, b, CH₂^{Pz}), 7.18 (4H, t, $^3J_{H-H} = ^3J_{H-F}$ 8.7 Hz, 3-H^{Ar}), 7.44 (1H, t, $^3J_{H-H}$ 7.6 Hz, 4-C^{Ph}), 7.56 (2H, t, $^3J_{H-H}$ 7.6 Hz, 3-C^{Ph}), 7.65–7.68 (6H, b, 2-H^{Ar}, 2-H^{Ph}); ¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : -151.5 (BF₄⁻), -113.5 (Ar-F); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, methanol-*d*₄) δ (ppm) : 3.09 (4H, b, CH₂CH₂S^{Ar}), 4.27 (4H, b, CH₂^{Pz}), 7.13 (4H, t, $^3J_{H-H}$ 8.4 Hz), 7.43 (3H, b), 7.59 (6H, b); the third aliphatic group could not be detected because its signal overlapped with the residual proton signal of the solvent; the broadness of the aromatic peaks prevented their assignment. ¹⁹F NMR (282 MHz, methanol-*d*₄) δ (ppm) : -154.8 (BF₄⁻), -114.0 (Ar-F); MS (ESI+, MeOH) : *m/z* (%) = 567.2 [HL+Na]⁺ (20), 653.0 [AgL+H]⁺ (32), 713.1 [AgL(OAc)+2H]⁺ (10), 1111.1 [(HL)₂+Na]⁺ (7), 1197.1 [AgL₂+2H]⁺ (100), 1303.0 [Ag₂L₂+H]⁺ (27), 1410.9 [Ag₃L₂]⁺ (15).

[PdL²]₂(BF₄)₂ (5) : A solution of [Pd(MeCN)₄](BF₄)₂ (28 mg, 63.0 × 10⁻³ mmol, 3.0 equiv.) in CH₂Cl₂ (4

mL) and MeCN (1 mL) was added to a solution of $[\text{AgL}_2]_3$ (**2**) (41 mg, 20.9×10^{-3} mmol, 1.0 equiv.) in CH_2Cl_2 (5 mL). The resulting mixture was stirred for 2 h, while the color changed from colorless to orange. The crude material was isolated by removing the solvent under reduced pressure. Yellow crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction were obtained by layering Et_2O over a solution of the crude material in MeCN. ^{19}F NMR (282 MHz, CD_3CN) δ (ppm) : -151.8 ($^{11}\text{BF}_4$), -151.7 ($^{10}\text{BF}_4$), -115.42, -115.40 (Ar-F); MS (ESI+, MeCN) : m/z (%) = 650.0 $[\text{Pd}_2\text{L}_2]^{2+}$ (100), 1145.0 (4), 1326.0 (2), 1387.0 $[\text{Pd}_2\text{L}_2(\text{BF}_4)]^+$ (8), 1413.0 (2).

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